

SPORTS IN MODERN LIFE AND ITS IMPORTANCE.

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Annotasiya : Ushbu maqolada sportning zamonaviy hayotdagi ahamiyati, sportning shaxsiy rivojlanishga ta'siri va sportning butun jamiyatga qanday ta'sir qilishini aniqlashga qaratilgan tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan.

Annotation. The article presents the results of a study aimed at revealing the importance of sport in modern life, the impact of sport on the development of personality and how sport affects society as a whole. Ключевые слова: спорт, физические культура, досуг. Keywords: sports, physical culture, leisure.

People around the world have varying attitudes toward sport, and it plays a specific role in everyone's life. Some are completely indifferent to sport, considering it a waste of time, while others understand its purpose, and there are more of them than the former. Moreover, each of these people has a different attitude toward sport: some prefer to watch it on television, others engage in a particular sport or general physical training, and for others, sport is a means of livelihood. These include active athletes, coaches, doctors, directors of sports societies, sports trustees, and others, and each of them contributes to the development of sport [1].

Sport has its own unique characteristics: it helps people get to know each other and bond with one another, and in the vast majority of cases, it strengthens health, character, and enhances mental abilities. People who play sports develop skills such as endurance, patience, strength, agility, speed, reaction time, coordination, and stamina. It also helps them become more resilient to stress and negative environmental factors, and they experience a wealth of positive emotions when, for example, their favorite team wins or they achieve a specific result [3].

With technological advances, people strive to simplify their lives, and physical labor loses its significance, gradually losing their inherent physical potential. Alcohol and drug use, as well as smoking, also have a negative impact on humanity. In this case, sports provide an alternative to these negative factors

and help prevent people from becoming alcoholics, drug addicts, or smokers. Therefore, the role of sports in our lives is very significant and important.

Sport is an activity of people that is organized according to certain rules and consists of comparing their intellectual and physical abilities, where preparation for this activity and the relationships between them that arise in its process are of great importance [2].

Sport is a component of physical education, the purpose of which is competition and preparation for it. It is expressed in a person's desire to win and achieve higher results, while utilizing all their mental, moral, and physical qualities. Participation in mass sports provides an opportunity for a huge number of people to improve their motor skills and physical abilities, strengthen their health, and increase their lifespan [4].

High-performance sport is a form of activity in which outstanding record-breakers push virtually all bodily systems to the limits of a healthy person's physical and practical capabilities. The primary goal in high-performance sport is achieving the highest possible athletic results and victories at major competitions.

Leisure culture has recently developed significantly, making various sporting competitions and spectating them a very popular pastime among the population, and for athletes, it has become a professional activity. Professional athletes who achieve high results are popular among both fans and the general population; they earn huge salaries and also generate income through product endorsements.

To regulate professional sports, special organizations and associations are created that bring together athletes, their coaches, referees, and, in some cases, fans. Sports have become a business and a source of wealth, which greatly influences the content of competitions. Sports rules are frequently changed to suit the needs of the audience or the convenience of referees.

In Uzbekistan, sport is one of the most popular activities, practiced both professionally and amateurly. Amateur sport is closely linked to the concept of "physical education." Unfortunately, both disciplines are not promoted and developed as actively in our country as modern achievements and progress require. A large number of Russian children participate in various sports clubs. For example, mass events such as the "Ski Track of Russia" and "Cross of Nations," as well as various summer and winter sports games based on the Spartakiads of the former USSR, are held. As a rule, all these events take place in districts, regional centers, and capital cities, while children from remote villages are forgotten, despite the fact that most Soviet athletes hailed from these villages and

went on to become World, European, and USSR champions, as well as Olympic medalists.

Achieving high results at the most prestigious sporting competitions, such as World and European Championships and the Olympic Games, in various sports demonstrates that many Uzbek sports schools occupy leading positions globally. Most Uzbek athletes are rightfully considered global sports stars, such as in boxing.

One important feature is the strong tradition of empathizing with participants in sporting events in Uzbekistan. The most popular summer sports among fans are both individual and team sports, such as football, swimming, tennis, track and field, basketball, and others

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